

The Role of Jadid Heritage in Forming Religious Tolerance and Interethnic Harmony among Youth

Halimov Eminjon Zaripovich

Candidate of Psychological Sciences, Associate Professor

Kurbanov Djamshid Djurayevich

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philosophical Sciences

Abstract: This article analyzes the significance of an educational approach in fostering religious tolerance and interethnic harmony in the spiritual and educational views of Central Asian enlighteners. It explores the role of these ideas in shaping young people's worldview and countering malicious ideologies. Additionally, the study highlights the role of religious tolerance and interethnic harmony in ensuring social stability and provides an in-depth examination of Abdurauf Fitrat's views on the subject.

Key points: Development strategy, fundamentalism, moral education, social network, religious tolerance, interethnic harmony, spiritual heritage.

INTRODUCTION. Historically, Central Asia has been a region where diverse cultures, languages, customs, lifestyles, and religions coexisted. The region's position at the crossroads of trade routes and the development of diplomatic relations between various states significantly influenced the religious and cultural life of its people. This historical process played a crucial role in forming the principles of religious tolerance and interethnic harmony.

Today, in the context of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy, strengthening interethnic harmony and religious tolerance is one of the primary tasks. To effectively implement this process within society, it is essential to rely on our historical heritage. In this regard, the intellectual legacy of Central Asian Jadids, particularly Abdurauf Fitrat, holds significant scientific and practical relevance.

Materials.

THE JADID HERITAGE AND RELIGIOUS TOLERANCE. The Jadid movement, which emerged in the late 19th and early 20th centuries in Central Asia, was aimed at national awakening, scientific progress, and societal reform. The Jadids promoted crucial ideas to ensure religious tolerance and interethnic harmony.

In his works, Abdurauf Fitrat emphasized the necessity of fostering tolerance, unity, and compassion among people. He advanced the idea that "humanity requires kindness and love" and stressed the need to strengthen brotherhood among individuals¹. According to Fitrat, ensuring social peace and stability is a fundamental factor in human society.

The spiritual heritage of the Jadids serves as an effective tool in countering religious extremism, fanaticism, and radicalism. Their primary goal was to establish rational thinking within society

¹ Abdurauf Fitrat. Najot yo'li. T.: "Sharq", 2001., -B.195-196

through education. Therefore, utilizing the legacy of the Jadids in promoting religious tolerance remains highly relevant today.

Research and methods.

EDUCATING YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF RELIGIOUS TOLERANCE AND PEACEFULNESS. In the era of globalization, with increasing religious conflicts, radicalism, and violations of equal rights, educating youth in the spirit of tolerance has become particularly important. The following aspects should be considered:

1. **Strengthening moral education** – It is crucial to nurture young people based on national and universal values. Fitrat emphasized that moral upbringing plays a fundamental role in the physical and intellectual development of children.
2. **Promoting knowledge and enlightenment** – Education is the primary means of preventing youth from succumbing to religious fundamentalism and extremist ideologies.
3. **Explaining national and religious values** – It is necessary to protect young people from harmful ideologies by teaching them historical heritage and the scholarly works of great ancestors.

Discussion.

PRINCIPLES OF HARMONY AND TOLERANCE IN THE JADID WORLDVIEW

The Jadids studied global development trends and sought to adapt them to local conditions. The works of Fitrat and other Jadids indicate that they viewed science, education, and upbringing as key factors of progress.

Fitrat regarded moral education as the foundation of social stability and emphasized the importance of raising the younger generation with a spirit of tolerance. He also pointed out that moral perfection is closely linked to intellectual and physical development, stressing the necessity of instilling ethical values in children from an early age².

CONCLUSION. Today, Uzbekistan is implementing large-scale reforms aimed at strengthening interethnic harmony and religious tolerance. Educating young people in this spirit, providing them with knowledge, and instilling national values remain of paramount importance. In this context, an in-depth study of the spiritual heritage of the Jadids, particularly Abdurauf Fitrat, and its integration into the education system can contribute to the active participation of modern youth in socio-political life.

Ensuring a sound worldview among the younger generation and fostering their commitment to maintaining social stability are among the most urgent tasks of our time. Therefore, the legacy of the Jadids remains one of the primary sources for shaping a culture of tolerance, harmony, and humanism among youth.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Yangi O‘zbekiston strategiyasi [Matn] /Sh.M. Mirziyoev. - Toshkent: “O‘zbekiston” nashriyoti, 2021. – 464 b.
2. Abdurauf Fitrat. Najot yo‘li. T.: “Sharq”., 2001., -207 b.
3. Abdurauf Fitrat. Oila, T.: “Ma’naviyat”., 1998. – 34 b.
4. Aminov, A. Jadidchilik harakati va uning ahamiyati. Tashkent: Fan., 2020
5. UNESCO. *The Role of Education in Promoting Tolerance and Peace*. Paris: UNESCO Publishing. 2015
6. Halimov E., Abdug‘affor Xon., Ma’naviyat – komillik mayog‘i., “Buxoro” nashriyoti., - 2014., -B.6-7

² Abdurauf Fitrat. Najot yo‘li. T.: “Sharq”., 2001., -B.198